

EMOTIONS IN CHILDREN'S LITERATURE

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Abstract:

The present study aims to highlight some emotions, themes, directions and ethical aspects revealed in children's literature. Emotions in the classroom influence how children learn and the quality of their act of learning. The analysis focuses on certain works that approach emotions, which are everywhere, in every story and in every situation, with the aim of acquiring the theme of socio-emotional education, considered by some to be the missing piece of the contemporary pedagogical proposals.

Keywords: children's literature, pedagogy, emotions, language, imagination.

Children's literature is one of the first expressive tools that helps in understanding the world, supporting the child's development on several levels. Intelligent, critical and conscious, free and uninterested, well-guided reading matures the critical spirit and independent judgment, broadens cognitive horizons, nurtures the imagination, unchains creativity and divergent thinking, educates the aesthetic sense, and provides experience and knowledge of the world and society. At the same time, it enriches the lexicon and vocabulary, cultivating the literary language, fighting against the pauperized and standardization of language that occurs within our culture.

Jerome Bruner, an American psychologist, states that the functioning of the mind is based on the continuous growth of "networks of mutual expectations" of human beings who share the ability to read "other minds", to interpret the beliefs, desires, mental states, intentions of others, relating them with their self. Regarding this, culture returns to yield a central role in education and training. According to J. Bruner (1983:278), humans are characterized by the faculty to create "through the constitutive power of our symbol-making, our institutions, our culture-making", namely the capacity to build "possible worlds" that exceed biological limitations (2012a:6). He believed that we create or

constitute the world and the self through ourselves. (Bruner:1986: 130), and education presupposes an open formation, the result of a reflexive, interpretative and not only explanatory, cultural and narrative mind.

First, literature proposes critical issues, autonomy and judgement, freedom of thought and opinion or interpretation. It is a powerful and widespread diffuser of ideas, it gives a glimpse of another world, different value systems and ways of life, representing gaps to other worlds or cultures. In human history, in totalitarian eras, the book has been banned and persecuted as potentially subversive (except for its enslavement) by all authoritarian regimes and in all eras of gross obscurantism, as a "medium of freedom". Then, it offers intense emotional satisfaction, opening to unimagined worlds, talking about affectivity and emotions, shaping character and will. Reading, guided by age-appropriate and implicitly psychological development texts, offers valuable principles and promotes safe value orientations, develops attitudes of openness towards other people and cultures, induces feelings of sympathy and understanding towards "others".

Gianni Rodari sees literature as the place of all assumptions, providing the keys to entering reality in new ways, helping the child to know the world and educate his mind, because it confronts him with the main human problems in which he is emotionally involved and presents him with the complexity of reality in a simplified way, allowing him not only to discharge emotional tensions, but also to encourage the projection of internal experiences and the organization of knowledge and beliefs.

Emotions in the classroom influence how children learn and the quality of their learning. In the contemporary period, emotions, lack of self-confidence, self-esteem, anxiety, manifested prematurely, experienced a significant increase. The children of the contemporary generation have more emotional problems than in the past, they are more solitary, sorrowful, prone to anxiety, and in competitive situations they have very low confidence. One of the pedagogical goals is to improve dignity, confidence, positive expression of interests, skills, relationship and communication skills, through children's literature.

Since preschool age, multiple transformations take place, in terms of physical, cognitive, language development and emotional development. Socio-emotional development is the basis of the connections and

interactions that give meaning to children's experiences at all levels, it aims at the beginning of social life, their ability to perceive and express their emotions, to understand and respond to the emotions of others, a first step is the development of the concept of self, of the child's perception and self-image. Paul Ekman (2003: 13), studying emotions for over forty years, in different cultures, talks about the influence of emotions on the quality of life.

Emotional competences aim at recognizing and expressing emotions, understanding them, then regulating them. A first step in identifying one's own emotions in various situations, then those of others, identifying emotions associated with a specific context, transmitting affective messages and expressing empathy towards others. The second step includes the identification of the cause and consequences of emotions, in order to arrive at emotional regulation, which involves the acquisition by the child of some skills to manage them.

The pre-school and early school period is prefigured as the most important acquisitions, both physically, cognitively and socio-emotionally, it is the time when significant changes take place in the child's life, he becomes more independent, self-service behavior develops, psychic processes, the first elements of the socio-emotional domain take shape.

In general, social and emotional competence refers to the child's ability to perceive, understand, process, manage and express social and emotional aspects of one's own life, which is reflected in social skills, interpersonal skills, intrapersonal skills and emotional intelligence. It is fundamental to the adaptation of the individual, and certain components of its structure are strong predictors of academic success. Thus, children that lack social skills are usually shy, withdrawn children. They are rejected by the others, they are ridiculed, they are not included in the playgroup. The long-term consequences of the poor development of this competence are reflected in the learning plan (poor school results), in the emotional plan (anxiety, depression), in the social adaptation plan (school dropout, juvenile delinquency, substance abuse, etc.).

The fundamental psychic activity is the game, next to which is added literature as a resource for knowledge and broadening the child's horizons, for exploring oneself and others, the environment, etc., along with other activities that support the integral and harmonious

development of the child, with a view to its proper integration into society. Every child is born with a potential that nature has endowed him with. This potential must be known and developed so that the child can fulfill it. That is why it is important to provide affective and emotional support to the activity and all the experiences in which the child is involved, strengthening his ego.

Children's literature, adapting to the infantile mentality, characterized by animism and artificialism, has always had a pedagogical function of information, of knowledge, full of emotions and feelings, of visions of the world, giving the child the opportunity to face conscious fears and unconscious.

Literature helps schoolchildren to understand certain notions, they face different emotions, moods or feelings. Fear is at the center of many stories, because it is at the center of the child's life. There are fairy tales that present fear through creepy creatures, monsters that eat human beings, nightmarish landscapes, castles with rooms that hide the flames of hell, forests from which it seems impossible to escape, vengeful witches who, after years, demand reparations for the ancient insults; fairy tales that all end in a cathartic way. In fact, the child needs an external element to measure himself against, which is credible, fantastic and therefore far from himself and from being a real danger to him.

Looking from the perspective of the psychologist Bruno Bettelheim (1976), children need narratives with the help of which they can solve certain existential problems, certain fears, emotions and feelings, from separation anxiety, conflicts and rivalries: "Without such fantasies, the child does not get to know his monster better, nor is he given any suggestions as to how he can gain mastery over it. As a result, the child is left helpless in his worst anxieties - even more so than if he had been told fairy tales which give shape and body to these anxieties and also show him ways to overcome these monsters.' This is how he is shown the world of images, the characters so full of meaning that it becomes the food with which the consciousness is nourished. It is possible to immerse yourself in that world with the certainty that the shore is always there, within reach. Narrative helps it grow because it gives the child material to work with: it is the same material, laced with images and emotional references, that is also the building block of our

minds and provides food for reflection and opportunities to overcome our own frailties and insecurities.

The repertoire of children's works dealing with emotions is very rich, emotions are everywhere, in every story, on every page and in every situation, and in this article we will make some initial references.

The dot (2003), written by Peter H. Reynolds, is an inspirational story about encouragement, self-confidence and self-expression, distrust, anger, empathy, appreciation, joy and sharing. An "handbook for amazing people" where the author has compiled some "tools" to navigate the best possible journey: Patience. Obedience. Kindness. Perseverance. Curiosity ... and also a reminder to call for help when the going gets tough." In this award-winning story of self-expression and creativity, Vashti thinks she can't draw. But her teacher is sure she can. She knows that there is creative spirit in everyone, and she encourages Vashti to sign the frustrating point she angrily writes on a piece of paper. This act makes Vashti look at things a little differently and helps her discover that where there's a point, there's a way...a beginning. With wit, charm, and free-spirited illustrations, Peter H. Reynolds encourages even the most stubbornly uncreative among us to make a sign—and follow the path where it leads.

Christian Voltz's works also address a range of emotions, from anger, guilt, fear, sadness, to joy and courage. *It's not my fault!*, by Christian Voltz (2002), tells us about anger and guilt, about justification, fear and the courage to assume one's own responsibilities. *Petting a Butterfly* by Christian Voltz (2005) is a story that tackles the difficult subject of death for young children, talking about gratitude, concern, love, sadness, courage and acceptance. *Anything yet?* by Christian Voltz (2005) Waiting, Excitement, Boredom, Sadness, Anger, Patience, Accomplishment and Joy.

Jerôme Ruillier, author and illustrator of over twenty titles, reflects in a surprising and suggestive way the values of friendship and multiculturalism in the face of prejudice and xenophobia, delicately approaches difficult themes, about borders that must be erased.

Trace Moroney is another internationally acclaimed author and illustrator of children's books, her Feelings Series (*When I'm Feeling, My Emotions, When I'm Happy, When I'm Angry, When I'm Sad, When I'm*

Scared, When I'm Disappointed, When I'm Jealous, When I'm feeling love, When I'm feeling kind, When I'm Feeling Nervous, When I'm Feeling Happy) was a worldwide success, translated into seventeen languages. *My emotions* (*Stress anxiety and me, I am me, The Greif wave, etc.*), *The things I love*, launched in 2009, was received with tremendous enthusiasm, focusing on the concept of love and gratitude, providing examples of creating positive thoughts. Focused on creating "books with consciousness", Trace Moroney embraces the principles of positive psychology, focusing on what is good in the world. The time dedicated to children, the love and care with which we surround them helps them to understand more easily who they are and strengthens their self-confidence.

Frances Hodgson Burnett published *The Secret Garden* (2007) in installments in *American Magazine* in 1910, and then published it as a stand-alone text in 1911. The novel is a classic of children's literature and follows the adventures of two children, the orphan Mary and her cousin they, Colin, who are working to make a garden hidden by a high wall on Colin's father's estate and forgotten by him after his wife's death, which occurred in that very place, flourish again.

The Secret Garden presents many pedagogical ideas that are very modern compared to the education of the years in which it was conceived, both in terms of pedagogical theories and those regarding the regenerative power of nature and the healing power of "positive thinking". The text, in fact, claims an unprecedented ability of children to operate rationally and help each other out of a moment of crisis, a book that speaks of humiliation, anger, sadness, rejection, love, happiness, and hope. The characters in the novel therefore show that they can manage their time independently, without necessarily needing the strict supervision of an adult, promoting a psychological balance and new pedagogical ideas. The lives of the characters, in fact, are miserable as long as they indulge in fatal thoughts: Mary withdrawing into herself, Colin convinced of his own illness, and Lord Craven obsessively remembering the happiness of a married life lost forever. The three characters therefore gain both spiritual and physical strength from "positive thinking": Mary decides to revive a dead garden, Colin decides to show the world that he is not "a cripple" but a normal boy, and Lord Craven, admiring the prosperity of the garden and the

renewed energy of his son, he manages to forget the past. The education promoted by Burnett, therefore, is not that provided in dark classrooms, but that guaranteed by outdoor life and cooperation. Moreover, the two children are a boy and a girl, and again in this case Burnett acts against the dictatorship of the time: the excessive emotional closeness of two children of the opposite sex was actually judged inappropriate, while Burnett shows, through the evolution of his characters, how can also prove fertile in stimuli. This narrative makes them dream and reflect on the importance of thinking: negativity, left to act, would prevent them from moving forward. Another key element promoted by Burnett is the importance of being raised with affection. In this context, the key metaphor of the whole text fits: that of the garden, which should not be understood only as a physical place, but also as a place of the soul, to be cultivated and made to flourish after a problematic situation.

Astrid Lindgren (*The Brothers Lionheart* (2000), *Pippi Longstocking*, etc.) produced a literary revolution, through her authentic, absolutely non-conformist characters, through the innovation of mainly the female image, with a different image of childhood, introducing complex themes and issues from an existential perspective that he tackles bravely and unconventionally, introducing the mix of genres that lack obvious didacticism or authoritarianism.

In *Pippi Longstocking* they converge, in an original connection between children's and adult literature, about friendship, adventure, the joy of living, with adventures and discoveries combining some aspects of the fairy tale (for example, Pippi's hyperbolic power) with domestic humor and schoolboy. In *Ronja*, it mixes a variety of genres: fantasy, fairy tales, different aspects of adventure novels or a historical setting. In *The Lionheart Brothers* he addresses the themes (friendship, love, anger, injustice, loneliness, obedience, sacrifice, joy of living) and the specific characteristics of the Saga and Norse legends, fairy tales (monsters, the fight between good and evil, the trials or tests that are subject the hero).

Astrid Lindgren's novels offer horizons of meaning and thought-provoking stimuli, because they address subjects of interest, being subversive classics, because they are a hymn to freedom of thought, to the courage to criticize hypocrisies and injustices, offering the right to dream of alternative worlds. His characters are free, independent and

full of life, transgressive, break the rules and authority of adults out of curiosity to explore, are creative, playful and intelligent, resourceful in order to achieve goals, are also reflective, emotionally complex- affective and experience negative states, episodes of psychic conflict and intense hatred towards the oppressors.

She describes difficult situations, such as poverty, the abandonment of elderly people in nursing homes, the sad fate of orphans or adopted children, the exploitation of child labor, alcoholism, physical or mental violence, she proposes for debate the meaning of life and death and introduces difficult topics and heartbreaking, such as suicide and euthanasia.

James and the Giant Peach (1961), *George' Marvelous Medicine* (1981), *Dirty Beasts* (1983), *The Witches* (1983), *Matilda* (1988) are some of Roald Dahl's children's writings who address a range of emotions, states or feelings, from mistreatment, harassment, sadness, mistrust, hopelessness, to courage, revenge or happiness. Dahl's narratives highlight children's vulnerability to trauma, hatred shown to them through neglect, discrimination, abandonment or abuse, and torture. Childhood is sometimes described as a traumatic experience. According to J. Held (2014: 2), a common theme of Dahl's novels is the unhappy life of children: "our lives speak of the absurdity of human existence, the fact that there is an unbridgeable gap between what we expect or demand from life and what we know, what is true", and the children are the ones who act, stopping the abusive behavior, through rebellion.

The child characters in *The Witches*, *Matilda* and *James and the Giant Peach* are abused and helpless, but later emerge victorious by outwitting their abusers, ingenuity and a little magic. The adults are portrayed grimly as abusers who dominate and manipulate the young. R. Dahl's works depict the fears, anxieties and dark aspects of a child's life, sometimes too complicated and without a way out, but revenge on the aggressors is a punishment and satisfies the deep need for justice. K. Reynolds states that this tendency to change, to transform fear into something playful, helps children. (Reynolds, 2020). This type of approach to fears and emotional states nourishes and enriches children's imagination, favors and accelerates the process of personality maturation, satisfying deep emotional needs.

At preschool and school age, each reading has a great influence, and it is advisable to stimulate the child to independently produce stories, derived from previous readings. Imagination must be educated and cultivated, as mental capacity is considered fundamental for learning and the harmonious development of the child's personality, complementary to rational activity itself, indispensable for imagining and planning the future. Gianni Rodari suggests in his techniques the stimulation of imagination and creativity through narratives in which the child plays, reinventing, creating words, expressions, motifs and plots in a new and original way, giving life to a new narrative product. What is important is that the teacher or educator is himself a lover of reading and therefore conveys his passion to the little interlocutor.

A textual analysis of the pedagogical discourse, and therefore of the children's literature text, must take into account the dialectic between three dimensions: intratextuality, which is the structure of the text with its constituent elements and its internal dynamics; intertextuality, which is its relationship with other texts; extratextuality, which is the relationship with the context that the text generated.

Educating through storytelling is equivalent to conceiving education not only as a moment of explanation and transmission of knowledge, but also as a moment of mutual listening. Children's literature is constantly evolving, shaping itself around a well-defined age range and has become, at the same time, an educational and training tool and a vehicle for introducing children to reading, it has enriched itself with new languages and iconic communication - visual and thanks to the technological tools it uses, it has made its way of presenting itself more pleasant, adapting to the needs of an ever-expanding man with multiple characteristics.

Moreover, children's literature is not only a discipline in itself, but establishes interactive relationships with many other disciplines, which it contributes to the enrichment of and by which it is enriched in turn. Her greatest success, however, is due to the fact that, adapting to the infantile mentality, she knows how to speak to children, allowing them to face, through fantastic reworkings, the conscious or unconscious fears that torment them.

A literary classic is still an effective tool for communication and education because, according to Calvino's (1995) definition, "a classic is a book that has never finished saying what it has to say."

The teacher, by selecting and analyzing in class certain works for children, manages to create an integrative background capable of leading children in a process of identification and personal growth. Reading and analyzing the main features of the text is a theoretical premise that allows the organization of subsequent, integrative activities in which children, if properly encouraged by an adult, are able to understand and relate even to very complex subjects.

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